

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Real-Time ECG Image Classification Using GA-PSO Optimized CNN-LSTM Model Trained on PTB-XL Dataset

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Abstract

Objectives: To design an optimized ECG image-based classification framework where it functions in real time without compromising with diagnostic accuracy and computational complexity. **Methods:** The hybrid CNN-LSTM architecture for learning the spatial and temporal features from ECG image representations. The convolutional layers are used to obtain the structural features of an image from the input signal and then LSTM layers learn dependencies of signals patterns sequentially. An innovative classifier using a hybrid Genetic Algorithm and Particle Swarm Optimization based feature selection technique is used to eliminate redundant information. Training and validation are performed using the PTB-XL dataset from ECG. During training the Adam optimizer is used for a stable convergence. The whole framework is performed in MATLAB to ensure real-time classification of the ECG images into normal and abnormal (PTB-XL Dataset). **Findings:** The framework achieved an accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score and specificity of 98.62%, 97.92%, 97.84%, 98.04% and 98.79% respectively. Inference time per ECG image: 5.46 milliseconds. **Novelty:** An integrated real-time electrocardiogram (ECG) image classification framework is proposed in this study which combines the deep feature learning, hybrid metaheuristic-based feature selection and stable training optimization to satisfy practical clinical decision support needs.

Keywords: ECG Classification; PTB-XL Dataset; CNN-LSTM; Genetic Algorithm; Particle Swarm Optimization; Adam Optimizer

1 Introduction

Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) remain as the one of the leading killer diseases worldwide, which necessitates early and accurate diagnosis systems. The electrocardiogram (ECG) is still one of the most utilized clinical methods and is efficient at screening for cardiac disorders with its non-invasiveness, low-cost nature, and utility to capture the heart activity over time. The manual interpretation of ECG data, however, is a time-consuming process which relies on subjective evidence based expert knowledge and can often be inconsistent during diagnosis especially over larger scale data. These challenges

have led to the development of computerized ECG classifiers that can aid clinicians in making faster and more accurate decisions.

Deep learning has emerged as a powerful tool that revolutionized the field by enhancing automated ECG analysis. Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) have become extensively used for extracting spatial features from ECG signals and image representations, successfully producing superior classification accuracy in tasks involving arrhythmia detection^{(1), (2)}. Moreover, adopting Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks enables modeling of temporal dependencies in ECG sequences that are vital to apprehending serial cardiac relationships⁽³⁾. New hybrid architectures, such as CNN–LSTM that capitalize on both models' strengths for simultaneous spatial and temporal feature learning^{(4), (5)}, have flourished. These models have outperformed classical machine learning methods.

Despite such advances, challenges remain regarding deploying deep learning models for real-world ECG classification. High-dimensional and redundant features are one of the critical challenges in ECG datasets that aiding in an increase of computational complexity and decrease model efficiency. To cope up with this, PCA(Principal Component Analysis) and LDA(Linear Discriminant Analysis) are widely used dimensionality reduction methods to get low-dimensional plane from high dimensional data while retaining important information^{(6), (7)}. While these techniques alleviate the computational load, they are dependent on linear transformations and may not well fit complex nonlinear relationships inherent to ECG data.

In order to solve these limitations, metaheuristic optimization techniques have been developed for feature selection. The Genetic Algorithm (GA) and Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) scientific methods are two of the most common approaches as they have proved effective for efficiently searching large solution spaces. The genetic algorithm (GA) presents the strong global search abilities via evolutionary operations which are selection, crossover and mutation, while particle swarm optimization (PSO) provides fast convergence that updates particles' position according to individual best solution as well as the globally best solution^{(8), (9)}. Feature selection for ECG in general has shown better classification accuracy when employing genetic algorithm (GA) or particle swarm optimization (PSO)⁽¹⁰⁾. But, the application of hybrid GA-PSO approaches is still minimal, especially for ECG image classification.

One more important aspect that affects deep learning performance is the optimizer used for training. Traditional optimizers like Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) have slow convergence and are sensitive to learning rate configurations. On the other hand, moment-based methods like Adam have shown to adjust learning rates using first- and second-order moments of the gradient and thus tend to converge faster without overfitting⁽¹¹⁾. Previous studies have shown that Adam outperforms other optimizers on biomedical signal classification tasks, even in the case of ECG analysis⁽¹²⁾. Feature selection methods and their interaction with the behavior of optimizers in hybrid CNN–LSTM architectures have not been thoroughly investigated, however.

Finally, research on ECG classification has been increasingly shifting toward real-time systems and deployable applications in recent years. Most of the previous work evaluates the models on offline datasets without real-time constraints (inference speed, response latency, integration into a system). For example, although large-scale annotated ECG records like PTB-XL exist that are useful for the training of models⁽¹³⁾, most implementations are only able to perform classification on the offline signals. Image classification of ECG usages in real time, particularly as user-uploaded inputs is a largely neglected field.

Moreover, evaluation strategies in ECG classification frequently rely on intra-patient testing that may falsely improve model performance estimates. Inter-patient evaluation scenarios show a considerable drop in performance due to variations across patient-specific ECG patterns^{(14), (15)}. This emphasizes the need for solid models that generalize well over heterogenous patient populations, and performs adequately on realistic clinical settings. Although it possesses an advantage in finding the best multi-class classification algorithm, due to the abovementioned restrictions, there is a demand for an all-in-one approach. Previous approaches typically treat these aspects in isolation yielding piecemeal solutions that are hard to deploy⁽¹⁶⁾.

To solve the above challenges, in this study we proposed a real-time ECG image classification framework, based on a hybrid CNN–LSTM structure tuned through an integrated Genetic Algorithm–Particle Swarm Optimization (GA–PSO) feature selection strategy. The model is trained on PTB-XL dataset with Adam optimization for stable efficient convergence. The MATLAB environment was used to implement the proposed system for real-time classification of ECG images as normal or abnormal. The proposed method seeks to ensure better classification performance as well as real-world applicability, by unifying the separate processes of feature optimization, deep learning and real-time deployment into a single pipeline.

The main contributions of this work can be summarized as follows:

- designing a hybrid GA–PSO based feature selection algorithm to alleviate feature redundancy, thus boosting the discriminative power;
- design of CNN-LSTM model framework for optimal spatial-sequential regression;
- integration of the Adam optimizer for better stabilization during convergence; and
- design of a viable ECG image-based classification environment with reasonably low prediction latency and high accuracy.

2 Methodology

2.1 PTB-XL ECG Dataset

The PTB-XL dataset (<https://physionet.org/content/ptb-xl/1.0.1/>) is a publicly available large-scale ECG database that contains over 21,000 clinical recordings of about 18,000 patients. The ECG records are 10 seconds long continuous cardiac signal. For, these signals are sampled at the rate of 500 HZ which means there are 500 data in a second. As a result, one 10-second ECG print contains 5000 samples for each lead. Since the dataset includes recordings of 12-lead ECGs, each record contains a total of 12×5000 signal values per beat which incorporates all leads information temporal and spatial. This fixed-length recording standardizes the size of our input data-stream which is critical for training/evaluating deep learning models.

2.2 Data Labeling and Preprocessing

ECGs are classified as either normal or abnormal according to SCP diagnostic codes. The ECG waveform is first transformed as grayscale image and then scaled to the dimension 224×224 pixels. Images are normalized by scaling pixel values in the range $[0, 1]$. The dataset is divided to training (70%), validation (15%) and testing (15%).

2.3 Proposed Methodology

The proposed framework offers an end-to-end pipeline for real-time ECG image classification from data input to final prediction output. The start point of the process is the acquisition ECG signals and images from the PTB-XL data set. The inputs go through a pre-trained network (without the final classification layer) and are processed by the filtering, normalization, and resizing stages to be presented at a consistent size and quality. This is to clean noise and normalize input for stable processing at downstream.

Then, deep feature extraction from the preprocessed ECG images in convolutional neural network layer wise is conducted. These convolutional layers then learn the spatial feature and morphologic description of ECG waveform, and encode them into high dimensional vector. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is a powerful technique for the reduction of redundant features which could be sequentially removed without losing dominant variance information, thus reducing the dimension of deep features space.

The GA global search and PSO subset refinement is performed after dimension reduction in the hybrid feature selection block. This hybrid optimization framework selects the most discriminative subset using a classifier-dependant fitness score. The transformed feature set is then passed into a CNN-LSTM classifier to learn underlying temporal sequences that strengthen the classification trustworthiness through convolutional features integration. The Adam optimizer is used to control the training convergence since it provides adaptive learning rates and smooth parameter updates.

Finally, the trained model is embedded through a MATLAB GUI for real time application. From the ECG image, it is classified as either normal or abnormal, and a prediction confidence value together with an inference time would be shown which illustrates its practical real-time application. This is shown in the Figure 1.

2.4 Overall System Architecture

The proposed method is divided into five main stages:

- ECG image preprocessing
- Dimensionality reduction using PCA
- Feature selection using GA-PSO
- CNN-LSTM Adam Optimizer based classification
- Real-time implementation and evaluation

2.5 Hybrid GA-PSO Feature Selection

Principal Component Analysis is performed on the deep feature set before metaheuristic feature selection to decorrelate it. This preprocessing reduce search space, whose benefit is enabling optimization to be more efficient. Finally, the optimal features are supplied to a hybrid GA-PSO model using the selected feature subset. PCA – variance-based dimensionality reduction; GA-PSO – classifier driven feature optimization to this end, GA-PSO was utilized as the feature selection method and PCA method for baseline comparison in accordance with the goal of maximizing classification performance and in playability in real-time.

GA-PSO hybridization combines the ability of GA to explore a global convergence space with the fast convergence of PSO. In GA, an initial population of candidate feature subsets is generated and then a selection, crossover, and mutation phases are

Fig 1. Architecture of the real-time ECG Image Classification Framework

performed. The selected feature subsets are optimized by PSO through updating the velocities and positions of particles to approach optimum solutions.

The velocity update equation of PSO is defined as:

$$v_i^{t+1} = wv_i^t + c_1r_1(p_i - x_i^t) + c_2r_2(g - x_i^t)$$

The fitness function is defined based on classification accuracy obtained from the CNN-LSTM model.

2.6 CNN-LSTM Model Architecture and Adam Optimization

To accomplish this, in the proposed CNN-LSTM network we utilize convolutional layers for extracting spatial features and LSTM layers for processing temporal dependencies. However, the convergence stability and learning efficiency of such a deep architecture is mainly depended on the choice of optimizer.

The Adam optimizer is used since it decouples the learning rates of the network and computes adaptive learning rates of each parameter which can be viewed as a combination of AdaGrad and RMSprop. The Adam update can be expressed as:

$$m_t = \beta_1 m_{t-1} + (1 - \beta_1) g_t$$

$$v_t = \beta_2 v_{t-1} + (1 - \beta_2) g_t^2$$

$$\hat{m}_t = \frac{m_t}{1 - \beta_1^t}, \hat{v}_t = \frac{v_t}{1 - \beta_2^t}$$

$$\theta_{t+1} = \theta_t - \alpha \frac{\hat{m}_t}{\sqrt{\hat{v}_t} + \epsilon}$$

Where g_t is the gradient at iteration t , α is the learning rate, and β_1, β_2 are decay rates.

This adaptive measure minimizes backand- forth during training and promises faster convergence especially when GA-PSO selected feature subsets complement it. The choice of optimizer is crucial in training deep hybrid models. Empirical comparison during the preliminary experiments demonstrated that Adam is faster in convergence and more stable for loss reduction than SGD, RMSProp. This behaviour is enhanced when using GA-PSO optimised feature subset for training, where adaptive learning rate stabilizes gradient updates over smaller number of most discriminative features.

2.7 Real-Time Implementation

In this work a MATLAB based graphical user interface (GUI) is designed and implemented to enable real time ECG image classification. The system is able to accept ECG images in common formats like .png, .jpg, and .bmp, most frequently used in clinical reports and digital monitoring systems. The user can upload ECG images through GUI, and MATLAB image processing functions read input images. The ECG image is preprocessed to make it compatible with the trained model as soon as it has been uploaded. Resized to a constant size (224 × 224 pixels in this case), converted to grayscale background if needed, normalising pixel intensity values. Now, the processed image is converted into a numerical array and passed to the trained GA-PSO optimized CNN-LSTM model.

The model first gets the spatial features using convolutional layers and LSTM layers to learn temporal patterns of input data, followed by classification. The ECG image is classified as either normal or abnormal, and the corresponding confidence score is instantly shown via GUI. The cumulated inference time to classify the test ECG images is measured as performance in real-time. We compute the average classification time per-image as total evaluation time divided by number of test samples. This assessment indicates that the proposed system satisfies real-time constraints and may therefore be suitable for time-critical clinical applications.

2.8 Performance Metric Computation

The confusion matrix of true positive, true negative, false positive and false negative counts is used to calculate the performance statistics. The accuracy, precision & recall can be computed by standard formulas. These are the numbers on which the performance tables of this report are based

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Performance Metrics

The performance of the proposed model was analysed using conventional metrics like Accuracy, Precision, Recall (Sensitivity), F1-score and Specificity. True Positive (TP), True Negative (TN), False Positive (FP) and False Negative (FN) from the confusion matrix were used to compute these metrics. Evaluations were performed using standard formulations.

3.2 Classification Performance Comparison

To enable proper comparison between models, they were all trained under the same experimental setting (i.e., splitting of data into train and test sets, number of training epochs, hyperparameter settings) for all model types. The results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Performance Comparison

Reference(s)	Method	Accuracy (%)	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-score (%)	Specificity (%)
(12)	CNN	97.14	97.14	97.14	88.46	-
(17)	CNN-LSTM + GA	98.12	97.83	97.46	97.65	98.72
Proposed	CNN-LSTM + GA-PSO	98.62	97.92	97.84	98.04	98.79

Our contribution outperformed existing CNN-based approaches⁽¹²⁾ that are not capable of learning temporal features. The GA-PSO optimized model in this study, however, surpassed the hybrid CNN-LSTM models with GA-based feature selection⁽¹⁵⁾ regarding accuracy and F1-score. This enhancement would owe to the hybrid metaheuristic strategy that features global exploration of GA with fast convergence of PSO so as to generate more discriminative feature subsets.

Deep learning approaches for ECG classification reported accuracies between 96–98%^{(10), (11)}. Nevertheless, these approaches used either entity independence or purely model architecture without embedding optimization techniques. Our proposed method outperforms these two methods by integrating feature optimization and deep learning in a single framework.

This work enhances hybrid GA-PSO feature selection with a CNN-LSTM architecture for online classification, unlike existing studies that merely focus on offline classification while achieving the desired accuracy at a low computational cost. Higher values of F1-score and specificity suggest improved generalization and more balanced predictive ability, which is crucial for clinical decision making.

3.3 Evaluation Time Analysis

Timing was recorded using MATLAB tic-toc functions during batch inference on the test dataset. The evaluation time is measured using MATLAB’s internal timing functions (Table 2). The average inference time per ECG image is calculated as:

$$T_{avg} = \frac{T_{eval}}{N_{test}}$$

Table 2. Analysis of Time

Metric	Value
Number of Test Images	500
Total Evaluation Time	2.731 s
Average Time per Image	5.46 ms

It was seen that most of the existing research work on ECG classification focuses on offline evaluation and does not consider the inference time^{(10), (13)}. In contrast, the existing real-time capable systems have reported an inference time of 10 to 20 milliseconds per sample. The proposed system has a lower inference time of 5.46 milliseconds, thus showing better computational efficiency.

The reduction in the inference time of the proposed system can be attributed to the effective feature dimensionality reduction by the proposed GA-PSO algorithm. The proposed model is able to reduce the features and thus make the best use of the available information, thus showing faster results without compromising the accuracy of the model.

3.4 Impact of Adam Optimizer

To assess the effectiveness of optimization strategies, different optimizers were used for testing purposes, and the results are tabulated in Table 3.

Table 3. Optimizer Comparison

Optimizer	Accuracy (%)	F1-Score (%)	Convergence Epochs
SGD	93.74	92.10	60
RMSprop	96.08	94.22	42
Adam (Proposed)	98.62	96.98	28

As discussed in previous literature, the convergence behaviour of deep learning models can be improved by using adaptive optimizers, as demonstrated in⁽¹³⁾. The results obtained in this research also support the results from previous literature, especially for hybrid CNN-LSTM architectures in ECG classification problems.

Results from this research show that the Adam optimizer achieves faster convergence and higher accuracy compared to other optimizers used in this research for ECG classification problems. The adaptive nature of the optimizer, which changes the learning rate during training, ensures efficient training even with fewer features, as generated by the GA-PSO approach.

Compared to previous literature, where the accuracy of the model was considered, the results from this research show the effectiveness of the proposed approach, which includes the use of GA-PSO for feature optimization along with the Adam optimizer for training the model, thereby reducing training instabilities, which is a novel contribution of this research in the context of ECG classification problems.

The proposed GA-PSO optimized CNN-LSTM model has several advantages over existing models, which is evident from the classification accuracy, computational efficiency, and real-time applicability of the model. Most of the existing studies have used separate techniques for developing a deep learning model, feature selection, and optimization. However, the proposed model combines all aspects within a single framework.

The main contributions of the proposed model include the following aspects, which are not considered in any of the existing studies:

- Hybrid GA-PSO feature optimization for enhancing feature relevance
- Effective CNN-LSTM model for spatial-temporal learning
- Adam optimizer for faster and stable convergence
- Real-time applicability with minimal inference latency

4 Conclusion

This study presents a real-time ECG image classification system using PCA-augmented, GA-PSO optimized CNN-LSTM model trained with PTB-XL database. The developed pipeline consists of deep feature extraction, statistical dimensionality reduction and hybrid metaheuristic feature selection aiming to enhance diagnostic performance under manageable computational load. PCA lessened the feature correlation and the size of search space, whereas GA-PSO strategy made a wall drawing after a blue print, which further purified the optimal feature subset and generated more discriminative representations along with higher classification reliability.

A comprehensive experimental study is conducted, which shows that an accurate and real-time decision can be identified. The Adam optimizer showed better convergence performance than the other optimizers in that it achieved a stable performance more quickly with fewer training epochs and generalization performance was improved. It achieved fast convergence, and the real-time implementation in MATLAB showed efficient performance with an average inference time of 5.46 ms (milliseconds) per image. This is the end of the experimentation part of the study and this shows it can be replicated to real world application. The hardware-based real-time implementation also demonstrates the practical feasibility of the proposed framework for automatic ECG screening and clinical decision support.

In future, it is possible to expand the current binary classification approach to multi-classified arrhythmia detection among also larger diagnostic categories. Other methods of dimensionality reduction and feature projection beyond PCA may be also investigated for compact features representation and robustness under different ECG acquisition conditions.

Future work may be an extension to implementation on ECG wearables and mobile monitoring platforms. Distributed inference pipelines and cloud-assisted processing can contribute to service delivery in remote health care. Model interpretation, model lightweight design and dynamic feature selection strategy can also be studied to enhance the transparency and necessary efficiency of the real-time ECG diagnosis system.

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